

DESIGN AND SIMULATION OF EV BATTERY CHARGER BASED ON RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCE WITH FUZZY LOGIC CONTROLLER

¹REDDI RAMAKRISHNA SAIKUMAR, ²Dr D VIJAYA KUMAR

¹ M tech student, Dept of EEE, *ADITYA INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, TEKKALI SRIKAKULAM, AP, India.*

²Professor(BE, MTECH & PHD), Dept of EEE, *ADITYA INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT, TEKKALI SRIKAKULAM, AP, India.*

ABSTRACT:

Study on renewable energy based Electric Lorry battery charging system is flourishing in the automobile market in the recent years. The intermittent nature of the renewable resource sources causes the grid linked renewable resource systems for Electric car battery billing applications. Therefore, an Electric Lorry battery charger making use of grid connected PV system is proposed in this paper. Off-board battery chargers need to be very carefully looked at this requirement for quick refuelling created a change in EV billing technology to focus on DC facilities. This theory makes use of fuzzy logic to control energy intake and also EV battery charger utilizing SEPIC as well as BIDC (Bidirectional) converter. The Fuzzy reasoning control is utilized to merge the advantages of stable current control and constant voltage control. Unclear reasoning is appropriate for such executions. This strategy will help design the dynamics of nonlinear systems. Simulink determined as well as executed the solar-power system using photovoltaic cells, DC-DC converters, batteries, as well as fuzzy reasoning controllers.

Keywords: *EV, DC, SEPIC, BIDC, PV system.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Technical improvement has genuinely altered format and taken brand-new annoying situations to resolve a chain of troubles. Every one year, logo-new capabilities are delivered to cars. Security structures and manipulate functions absorb electric powered power even if engines are off. Battery p.C. May be placed indoor or outdoor the auto (off-board). An off-board charger is advanced to promote fast charging. This is certainly hundreds just like filling station. It offers an excessive output voltage. This can probable be the suitable desire for industrial use. Implementing this method might in all likelihood damage battery percent similarly to motive excessive energy call for. Due to upgrades in the solid-united states of America digital converters, photovoltaic structures have

in reality turn out to be an enormous vacation spot for micro grids that produce electric strength through way of feeding electricity proper into the general grid throughout height hours. Photovoltaic systems may be hooked up in families to deliver charging stations for electric powered vehicles. Battery chargers are mainly cut up proper into unmarried-stage and additionally -degree designs. Single-degree topology has the gain of lower weight, low amount, streamlined layout, and additional overall performance. Battery structures are categorized into 1/2 of of-bridge, complete bridge, multilevel, and separated AC-DC.

Ever in advance than developing results of greenhouse gases from the same old IC engines reason ecological problems. This paved to the thriving of infection complimentary electric powered